

NSA Screening Tool for Multiple Stakeholders

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INTRODUCTION

An urban system can be regarded as a system consisting of smaller building blocks such as neighbourhoods. The sustainability of an urban system is hence closely connected to the sustainability of neighbourhoods. Neighbourhood Sustainability Assessment (NSA) tools have multiple potential benefits for urban development such as a holistic evaluation and in some cases quantification of potential economic, social, environmental, and institutional impacts, quality assurance, improved cross-functional teamwork, improved processes etc. Nevertheless there are as yet a reluctance encountered from investors and municipalities in terms of applying NSA tools for developing neighbourhoods due to e.g. cost, complexity. Even a sustainability pre-certification is according to the existing NSA tools comprehensive, time consuming and not necessarily economical rewarding in the short run. Due to these obstacles related with the deployment of NSA tools even at entry level (pre-certification) are jeopardizing sustainable development of urban sub-systems and sustainability is therefore at risk of being neglected in urban development projects.

METHODS

Case studies and literature studies will provide information on sustainability criteria in the pre-design phase of neighbourhood development. Criteria will initially be extracted from the recently introduce DGNB New Urban District standard, which has been adapted by the Green Building Council Denmark for Danish regulations and norms, to provide information to the screening tool.

IDEA

The idea is to develop an open source digital screening system for the pre-design phase of neighbourhood developments which addresses relevant sustainability criteria and indicators ideally from various certification schemes, however initially primarily based on the DGNB system.

A questionnaire based assessment setup is provided for the stakeholders to provide an assessment focus and thereby to assist the stakeholders in prioritising their sustainable targets. Further will the questionnaire provide an evaluation of the stakeholder's political sustainability preferences and to be used for calculation of sustainability criteria weighting factors, thus providing a subjective importance of the individual criteria which can range from e.g. 1 to 10. The screening tool will through the questionnaire setup further provide an indication of sustainability focus in the pre-design phase of urban development through a prioritisation template for each stakeholder. Thereby will the tool provide the involved stakeholders with knowledge about each other's prioritisation and can e.g. build consensus among the stakeholders to attain a common sustainable agenda for the project specific for the neighbourhood being developed.

A flexible screening solution can help enhance stakeholder impact, and thereby the stakeholder's interest and willingness to adapt a NSA tools in the further process of the project. The screening tool can furthermore be used to weight and prioritise sustainable aspects and thereby consider project specific and stakeholder prioritising, if acknowledged by third party NSA tool developers.